

DIRECT PRODUCT OF ANTI \mathcal{N} -H-IDEALS IN BCK -ALGEBRAS

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we introduce the notion of anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of a BCK -algebra. Then, the notion of the direct product of two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals by using minimum operation is introduced, and some related properties are studied. Ordinary H-ideals are linked with anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals by means of an anti \mathcal{N} -s-level set of the direct product of two \mathcal{N} -structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of BCK -algebras was introduced by Imai and Iséki [12] in 1966. BCK -algebras have been applied to many branches of mathematics, such as functional analysis, group theory, topology, probability theory. Since Imai and Iséki [12] introduced the concepts of ideals in BCK -algebras, many types of ideals in BCK -algebras have occurred, for instance, H-ideals, closed ideals, implicative ideals, positive implicative ideals, and so on.

A crisp set C in a universe X is a function $\lambda_C : X \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ yielding the value 0 for elements excluded from the set C and the value 1 for elements belonging to the set C . As a generalization of crisp sets, Zadeh [20] introduced the degree of positive membership in 1965 and defined the concept of fuzzy set theory. This concept was applied to a BCK -algebra by Xi [19]. Jun et al. [14] presented a new function which is called negative-valued function, and developed \mathcal{N} -structure as one of the hybrid models of fuzzy set. They applied the idea of \mathcal{N} -structure in BCK -algebras and proposed \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and \mathcal{N} -ideals [14]. In [13], Jun established the definition of doubt fuzzy subalgebras and ideals in BCK -algebras. Al-Masarwah et al. [10] introduced the notions of doubt \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and ideals in BCK -algebras, and discussed several properties. After that, many Hybrid models of fuzzy sets were applied in BCK -algebras and other algebraic structures [5, 6, 8, 7, 9, 4, 17, 18, 2, 1, 3, 16, 15].

In this paper, we discuss an \mathcal{N} -structure with an application to BCK -algebras. We introduce the notion of anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals in a BCK -algebra. Also, we considered the structure of a BCK -algebra and defined the direct product of two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals. We present some interesting results about direct product of two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of a BCK -algebra.

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Finally, we proved that the direct product of two anti \mathcal{N} -structures becomes an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal if and only if for any $s \in [-1, 0]$, an anti \mathcal{N} - s -level set is an H-ideal of a BCK -algebra $X \times Y$.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we include some basic definitions and preliminary facts about a BCK -algebra which are essential for our results. By a BCK -algebra, we mean an algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ satisfying the following axioms for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- (I) $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
- (II) $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- (III) $x * x = 0$,
- (IV) $0 * x = 0$,
- (V) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

Any BCK -algebra X satisfies the following axioms for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- (11) $x * 0 = x$,
- (12) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$,
- (13) $x * y \leq x$,
- (14) $(x * y) * z \leq (x * z) * (y * z)$,
- (15) $x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z, z * y \leq z * x$.

A partial ordering \leq on a BCK -algebra X can be defined by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. A non-empty subset K of a BCK/BCI -algebra X is called:

- (1) A subalgebra of a BCK -algebra X [12] if $x * y \in K, \forall x, y \in X$,
- (2) An ideal of a BCK -algebra X [12] if $\forall x, y \in X$,
 - $0 \in K$,
 - $x * y \in K$ and $y \in K$ imply $x \in K$.
- (3) An H-ideal of a BCK -algebra X [11] if $\forall x, y, z \in X$,
 - $0 \in K$,
 - $((x * y) * z) \in K$ and $y \in K$ imply $x * z \in K$.

Definition 2.1. [21] A fuzzy set $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ in a BCK -algebra X is called an anti (a doubt) fuzzy H-ideal of X if

- (1) $\mu_A(0) \leq \mu_A(x)$,
- (2) $\mu_A(x * z) \leq \max\{\mu_A(x * (y * z)), \mu_A(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Denote by $\mathcal{F}(X, [-1, 0])$ the collection of functions from a set X to the interval $[-1, 0]$. We say that, an element of $\mathcal{F}(X, [-1, 0])$ is a negative-valued function from X to $[-1, 0]$ (briefly, \mathcal{N} -function on X). By an \mathcal{N} -structure we mean an ordered pair (X, ϕ) , where ϕ is an \mathcal{N} -function on X . In what follows, ϕ is an \mathcal{N} -function on X unless otherwise specified.

In [14], Jun et al. introduced the concepts of \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and \mathcal{N} -ideals in a BCK -algebra as follows:

Definition 2.2. An \mathcal{N} -structure (X, ϕ) is called an \mathcal{N} -subalgebra of X if for all $x, y \in X$:

$$\phi(x * y) \leq \max\{\phi(x), \phi(y)\}.$$

Definition 2.3. An \mathcal{N} -structure (X, ϕ) is called an \mathcal{N} -ideal of X if for all $x, y \in X$:

- (1) $\phi(0) \leq \phi(x)$,
- (2) $\phi(x) \leq \max\{\phi(x * y), \phi(y)\}$.

3. DIRECT PRODUCT OF ANTI \mathcal{N} -H-IDEALS

In this section, we introduce the concept of an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal. Then, we give the definition of the direct product of two \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of two BCK -algebras X and Y , and we provide some of its properties.

In what follows, X and Y are BCK -algebras, so we use $(X \times Y; *, (0, 0))$ to denote a BCK -algebra unless otherwise specified. For the sake of brevity, we call $X \times Y$ a BCK -algebra.

Definition 3.1. An \mathcal{N} -structure (X, φ) is called an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of X if it satisfies the following conditions for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- (1) $\varphi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$,
- (2) $\varphi(x * z) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * (y * z)), \varphi(y)\}$.

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ be a BCK -algebra with the following Cayley table:

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	a
b	b	a	0	b
c	c	c	c	0

Let (X, φ) be an \mathcal{N} -structure in which φ is given by:

$$\varphi(x) = \begin{cases} -0.1, & \text{if } x = 0 \\ -0.2, & \text{if } x = a, b, c. \end{cases}$$

Then by routine calculation, we know that (X, φ) is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of X .

Definition 3.3. Let $(X, *_X, 0_X)$ and $(Y, *_Y, 0_Y)$ be two BCK -algebras. The direct product of X and Y is defined to be the set $X \times Y = \{(x, y) \mid x \in X, y \in Y\}$. In $X \times Y$ we define the product $*_{X \times Y}$ as follows:

$$(x, y) *_{X \times Y} (u, v) = (x *_X u, y *_Y v) \text{ for all } (x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y.$$

One can easily verify that the direct product of two BCK -algebras is again a BCK -algebra. Now, we write the following definition.

Definition 3.4. Let X be a BCK -algebra and let (X, φ) and (X, ϕ) be two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of X . The direct product of (X, φ) and (X, ϕ) is defined by $(X \times X, \varphi \times \phi)$, where $\varphi \times \phi : X \times X \rightarrow [-1, 0]$ is given by

$$(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) = \min\{\varphi(x), \phi(y)\}$$

for all $(x, y) \in X \times X$.

In the following, we extend the above definition to the direct product of anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of any BCK -algebras X and Y .

Definition 3.5. Let X and Y be two BCK -algebras and let (X, φ) and (Y, ϕ) be two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of X and Y , respectively. Then, the direct product of (X, φ) and (Y, ϕ) is defined by $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$, where $\varphi \times \phi : X \times Y \rightarrow [-1, 0]$ is given by

$$(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) = \min\{\varphi(x), \phi(y)\}$$

for all $(x, y) \in X \times Y$.

Definition 3.6. An \mathcal{N} -structure $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ of a BCK -algebra $X \times Y$ is called an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$ if it satisfies the following conditions for all $(x, y), (u, v), (w, z) \in X \times Y$:

- (1) $(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)$,
 (2) $(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) \geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\}$.

Example 3.7. Consider a *BCK*-algebra $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and an anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideal (X, φ) of X which are given in Example 3.2. Define an anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideal (X, ϕ) in X as follows:

$$\phi(x) = \begin{cases} -0.3, & \text{if } x = 0 \\ -0.4, & \text{if } x = a, b, c. \end{cases}$$

Consider $(X \times X, \varphi \times \phi)$, where $(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) = \min\{\varphi(x), \phi(y)\}$ is defined as:

$$(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) = \begin{cases} -0.3, & \text{if } (x, y) = (0, 0), (a, 0), (b, 0), (c, 0) \\ -0.4, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

By routine calculations, we know that $(X \times X, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideal of $X \times X$.

Theorem 3.1. Let (X, φ) and (Y, ϕ) be two anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideals of *BCK*-algebras X and Y , respectively. Then, $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideal of $X \times Y$.

Proof. For any $(x, y) \in X \times Y$, we have

$$(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) = \min\{\varphi(0), \phi(0)\} \geq \min\{\varphi(x), \phi(y)\} = (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y).$$

Now, for any $(x, y), (u, v), (w, z) \in X \times Y$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) &= (\varphi \times \phi)(x * w, y * z) \\ &= \min\{\varphi(x * w), \phi(y * z)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\varphi(x * (u * w)), \varphi(u)\}, \min\{\phi(y * (v * z)), \phi(v)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\varphi(x * (u * w)), \phi(y * (v * z))\}, \min\{\varphi(u), \phi(v)\}\} \\ &= \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x * (u * w)), (y * (v * z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\} \\ &= \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideal of $X \times Y$. \square

Proposition 3.2. Let $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ be an anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideal of $X \times Y$. If $(x, y) \leq (u, v)$, then $(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)$ for all $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$.

Proof. Let $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$ such that $(x, y) \leq (u, v)$. Then, $(x, y) * (u, v) = (0, 0)$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) &= (\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (0, 0)) \\ &\geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (0, 0))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\} \\ &= \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (u, v)), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\} \\ &= \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\} = (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)$ for all $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$. \square

Proposition 3.3. Let $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ be an anti \mathcal{N} -*H*-ideal of $X \times Y$ such that

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (u, v)) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)$$

for all $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$. Then, $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an \mathcal{N} -constant.

Proof. Note that in a *BCK*-algebra $X \times Y$, $(x, y) * (0, 0) = (x, y)$ for all $(x, y) \in X \times Y$, and by using the assumption, we have

$$(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) = (\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (0, 0)) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0).$$

It follows from Definition 3.6, $(\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) = (\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0)$ for all $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$. Therefore, $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an \mathcal{N} -constant. \square

Proposition 3.4. *Let (X, φ) and (Y, ϕ) be two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of X and Y , respectively. If $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$, then $\varphi(0) \geq \phi(y)$ and $\phi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$ for all $x \in X, y \in Y$.*

Proof. Assume that $\varphi(0) < \phi(y)$ and $\phi(0) < \varphi(x)$ for some $x \in X, y \in Y$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) &= \min\{\varphi(x), \phi(y)\} \\ &> \min\{\varphi(0), \phi(0)\} \\ &= (\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0), \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. Thus, $\varphi(0) \geq \phi(y)$ and $\phi(0) \geq \varphi(x)$ for all $x \in X, y \in Y$. \square

Theorem 3.5. *Let (X, φ) and (Y, ϕ) be two \mathcal{N} -structures of X and Y , respectively, such that $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$. Then, either (X, φ) is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of X or (Y, ϕ) is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of Y .*

Proof. Since $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$, then for all $(x, y), (u, v), (w, z) \in X \times Y$, we have

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) \geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\}.$$

By putting $y = z = v = 0$, we have

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((x, 0) * (w, 0)) \geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, 0) * ((u, 0) * (w, 0))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, 0)\}. \quad (3.1)$$

Also, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi \times \phi)((x, 0) * (w, 0)) &= (\varphi \times \phi)((x * w), (0 * 0)) \\ &= \min\{\varphi(x * w), \phi(0 * 0)\} \\ &= \varphi(x * w) \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi \times \phi)((x, 0) * ((u, 0) * (w, 0))) &= (\varphi \times \phi)((x, 0) * ((u * w), (0 * 0))) \\ &= (\varphi \times \phi)((x * (u * w)), (0 * (0, 0))) \\ &= \min\{\varphi(x * (u * w)), \phi(0 * (0, 0))\} \\ &= \varphi(x * (u * w)). \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Again, by using Proposition 3.4, we have

$$(\varphi \times \phi)(u, 0) = \min\{\varphi(u), \phi(0)\} = \varphi(u). \quad (3.4)$$

So, from (3.1), (3.2), (3.3) and (3.4) we get, $\varphi(x * w) \geq \min\{\varphi(x * (u * w)), \varphi(u)\}$. Hence, (X, φ) is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of X . \square

Proposition 3.6. *Let $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ be an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of a BCK-algebra $X \times Y$. Then,*

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((0, 0) * ((0, 0) * (x, y))) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)$$

for all $(x, y) \in X \times Y$.

Proof. Note that

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\varphi \times \phi)((0, 0) * ((0, 0) * (x, y))) \\
& \geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((0, 0) * ((x, y) * ((0, 0) * (x, y)))), (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)\} \\
& = \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((0, 0) * ((x, y) * (0, 0))), (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)\} \\
& = \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((0, 0) * (x, y)), (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)\} \\
& = \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0), (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)\} \\
& = (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) \text{ for all } (x, y) \in X \times Y.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(\varphi \times \phi)((0, 0) * ((0, 0) * (x, y))) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)$ for all $(x, y) \in X \times Y$. \square

Corollary 3.7. *Let $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ be an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$. Then, the set*

$$D_{(\varphi \times \phi)} = \{(x, y) \in X \times Y \mid (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) = (\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0)\}$$

is an H-ideal of $X \times Y$.

Proof. Let $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ be an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$. Obviously, $(0, 0) \in D_{(\varphi \times \phi)}$. Let $(x, y), (u, v), (w, z) \in D_{(\varphi \times \phi)}$ be such that $(x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z)), (u, v) \in D_{(\varphi \times \phi)}$. Then,

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))) = (\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) = (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v).$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) & \geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\} \\
& = (\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0).
\end{aligned}$$

Again, since $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$, so $(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z))$. Therefore, $(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) = (\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z))$. It follows that $(x, y) * (w, z) \in D_{(\varphi \times \phi)}$ for all $(x, y), (u, v), (w, z) \in X \times Y$. Therefore, $D_{(\varphi \times \phi)}$ is an H-ideal of X . \square

Definition 3.8. Let $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ be an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$ and $s \in [-1, 0]$. Then, an anti \mathcal{N} - s -level set of $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is as follows:

$$(\varphi \times \phi)_s = \{(x, y) \in X \times Y \mid (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y) \geq s\}.$$

Theorem 3.8. *Let $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ be an \mathcal{N} -structure of $X \times Y$. Then, $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$ if and only if $(\varphi \times \phi)_s \neq \emptyset$ is an H-ideal of $X \times Y$ for all $s \in [-1, 0]$.*

Proof. Assume that $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$ and $s \in [-1, 0]$ such that $(\varphi \times \phi)_s \neq \emptyset$. Let $(c, d) \in (\varphi \times \phi)_s$. Then, we have $(\varphi \times \phi)(c, d) \geq s$. So we deduce that $(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(c, d) \geq s$. This shows that $(0, 0) \in (\varphi \times \phi)_s$. Let $(x', y'), (u', v'), (w', z') \in X \times Y$ such that $(x', y') * ((u', v') * (w', z')) \in (\varphi \times \phi)_s$ and $(u', v') \in (\varphi \times \phi)_s$. Then, $(\varphi \times \phi)((x', y') * ((u', v') * (w', z'))) \geq s$ and $(\varphi \times \phi)(u', v') \geq s$. Since $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\varphi \times \phi)((x', y') * (w', z')) \\
& \geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x', y') * ((u', v') * (w', z'))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u', v')\} \\
& \geq \min\{s, s\} = s,
\end{aligned}$$

so $(x', y') * (w', z') \in (\varphi \times \phi)_s$. Therefore, $(\varphi \times \phi)_s$ is an H-ideal of $X \times Y$.

Conversely, assume that $(\varphi \times \phi)_s \neq \emptyset$ is an H-ideal of $X \times Y$ for all $s \in [-1, 0]$. Let $(x, y) \in X \times Y$ be such that $(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) < (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)$. By taking

$$s_o = \frac{1}{2}[(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) + (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)],$$

we get $(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) < s_o < (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)$. Therefore, $(0, 0) \notin (\varphi \times \phi)_{s_o}$. This is a contradiction. Hence, $(\varphi \times \phi)(0, 0) \geq (\varphi \times \phi)(x, y)$ for all $(x, y) \in X \times Y$. Again, we assume that $(x, y), (u, v), (w, z) \in X \times Y$ be such that

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) < \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\}.$$

By taking

$$s_1 = \frac{1}{2}[(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) + \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\}],$$

we have

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) < s_1 < \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\}.$$

This shows that, $(x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z)) \in (\varphi \times \phi)_{s_1}$, $(u, v) \in (\varphi \times \phi)_{s_1}$, but $(x, y) * (w, z) \notin (\varphi \times \phi)_{s_1}$, this is a contradiction. Therefore,

$$(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * (w, z)) \geq \min\{(\varphi \times \phi)((x, y) * ((u, v) * (w, z))), (\varphi \times \phi)(u, v)\}$$

for all $(x, y), (u, v), (w, z) \in X \times Y$. Hence, $(X \times Y, \varphi \times \phi)$ is an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal of $X \times Y$. \square

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we introduced the notion of anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals in a BCK -algebra. Also, we considered the structure of a BCK -algebra and defined the direct product of two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals. We presented some interesting results about the direct product of two anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideals of a BCK -algebra. Finally, we proved that the direct product of two anti \mathcal{N} -structures becomes an anti \mathcal{N} -H-ideal if and only if for any $s \in [-1, 0]$, an anti \mathcal{N} - s -level cut set is an H-ideal of a BCK -algebra $X \times Y$.

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